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Who Wants to Leave the Academy: Educational Qualification and Age as Determinants of Turnover Intention?

¹Moses Ichongo Ukeh & ²Ignatius Hua Nyam

¹Department of Psychology

²Department of Liberal Studies

Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0021-1989>

E-mail: mosesukeh@polac.edu.ng superlifeconsulting@gmail.com

Abstract

Turnover intention among academic employees has become a significant concern for higher education institutions worldwide. This research investigates the influence of educational qualification and age on turnover intention among police academy employees. 75 employees (70 males and 5 females) with a mean age of 42.82 years and a standard deviation of 7.27 completed the 3-item Turnover Intention Scale. Three hypotheses were tested utilizing a two-way ANOVA (IBM SPSS 26) for the analysis. Our findings reveal significant main effects for both educational qualification, $F(3,67) = 12.02, p = .005$, with a large effect size (partial eta squared = 0.35), and age, $F(2,67) = 14.47, p = .005$, with a large effect size (partial eta squared = 0.30). However, there was no significant interaction effect, $F(2,67) = 2.37, p = .10$, indicating that the relationship between educational qualification and turnover intention does not vary with age. In conclusion, academic qualifications and age independently have an effect on turnover intention, but the effect is not moderated by age. This study provides new insights and extends knowledge on turnover intentions in higher education.

Keywords: Turnover intentions, educational qualifications, age, employees, police academy.

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Who Wants to Leave the Academy: Educational Qualification and Age as Determinants of Turnover Intention?**Introduction**

Employee turnover is a critical issue for organizations worldwide, significantly impacting operational continuity, employee morale, and financial stability (Al-Suraihi et al., 2021; Saeed, 2022). Arshad and Puteh (2015) argue that employee turnover, whether voluntary or involuntary, is potentially costly and could have negative consequences for organisations as well as personal costs (Samad, 2006). While turnover refers to when an employee of an organization leaves a job willingly (Ayele, 2022), turnover intention refers to an individual's psychological preparedness or tendency to leave a current job (Hesford et al, 2016). Therefore, turnover intention very often has the tendency to transform into turnover (Lasun & Nwosu, 2011), especially if there is a multitude of personal or organisational factors that reinforce such an employee's intentions to leave. In a higher educational institution like the academy, high turnover rates can lead to increased recruitment costs, disruptions in academic continuity, brain drain, excess workload for faculty and administrative staff, and loss of institutional knowledge (Saeed, 2022).

Turnover intention among employees is a precarious matter for higher education institutions, especially when it translates into actual turnover rates, as it can lead to disruptions in teaching, research, and administrative functions. Dissatisfied and frustrated employees are likely to display higher career plateau tendencies, less commitment, loyalty and intentions to leave (Zhang et al., 2017) than satisfied ones. When turnover rate increases, it exerts significant effects on existing employees, including stress due to extra workload. Low morale, job dissatisfaction, and associated stress can lead

to related health challenges (Haileyesus et al., 2019), making workplaces unsafe for employees. Usually, worker health-related costs due to absenteeism and presenteeism are substantial for both employers and employees (Nagata et al., 2018; Asay et al., 2016).

Previous research has identified various determinants of turnover intentions, including job stress (Alam, 2014), leadership (Puni et al., 2016; Siew, 2017), and work-life balance (Arshad & Puteh, 2015; Tetteh & Attiogbe, 2019) among others, Demographic factors such as age, educational qualifications, marital status, tenure, wage, position were studied as determinants of turnover intention (Akpa & Asikhia, 2016; Mulie & Sime, 2018). Other influencing factors, such as organisational justice (Ozturk et al., 2016; Tourani et al., 2016; Ukeh & Nyam, 2023), and job satisfaction have a significant negative association with turnover intention (Bashir & Durrani, 2014).

In the context of the Nigeria Police Academy, lack of organisational justice (Ukeh & Nyam, 2023), motivation and recognition, promotion, work-life balance, poor work and living conditions and remuneration are persistent precursors of turnover intention. Understanding the factors influencing turnover intention among employees is particularly important for the review of human resource policies to enhance the academy's role in training future police officers. Two prominent determinants of turnover intention identified in the literature are educational qualification and age (Akpa & Asikhia, 2016; Mulie & Sime, 2018). Abdali (2011, as cited in Mulie & Sime, 2018) also contends that demographic and individual attributes account for reasons employees leave an organisation.

Educational qualification is a critical factor in determining career trajectories in academia.

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Faculty members with higher qualifications, such as PhDs, may have different career aspirations and expectations compared to those with lower qualifications. This is indeed suggestive that faculty with advanced degrees will be more likely to seek opportunities for research and professional growth, and may experience higher turnover intention if these opportunities are not met. Similarly, Chen and colleagues (2022) in their study among Resident Doctors establish that high educational qualification often correlates with job satisfaction and career advancement opportunities, thereby influencing an employee's decision to stay or leave an organization (Chen et al., 2022). In summary, higher educational attainment can lead to higher expectations and a greater likelihood of seeking better opportunities elsewhere if those expectations are not met (Berg, 1991).

Age is another important determinant of turnover intention. Younger faculty members may be more mobile and open to exploring opportunities outside their current institution or even outside academia (Kirkpatrick, 2017). Conversely, older faculty members might exhibit lower turnover intention due to factors such as tenure, stability, and institutional loyalty. According to Ng and Feldman (2009), age affects turnover intention through its relationship with career stage and job stability. Younger employees may exhibit higher turnover intentions due to a greater propensity for career exploration and mobility, whereas older employees might seek stability and are less likely to leave (Staw, 1980). In contrast, research evidence also indicates no significant relationship between age and academic employee turnover intention in higher education institutions (Agmasu, 2020; Demlie & Endris, 2021; Haileyesus et al., 2019; Mulie & Sime, 2018), providing impetus for further studies.

The Human Capital Theory (HCT, Becker, 1975) provides a framework within which this research topic is situated. This theory posits that individuals' skills, knowledge, and experience, which are often influenced by their educational qualifications and age, affect their job performance and career decisions. In the context of turnover intention, HCT suggests that employees with higher educational qualifications may have greater opportunities and options in the job market, potentially increasing their turnover intentions. Similarly, age can influence turnover intentions, with younger employees possibly seeking career advancement and older employees considering retirement or career changes. Thus, this theory provides a comprehensive framework to understand how educational qualifications and age affect the turnover intentions of employees at the Nigeria Police Academy.

Understanding the factors that contribute to turnover intention is essential for developing effective retention strategies in the academy. However, the roles of educational qualification and age have been less explored. This study addresses this gap by examining how these factors interact to influence turnover intention among police academy employees. This study aims to investigate the effects of educational qualification and age on turnover intention among the employees of the Nigeria Police Academy. Three hypotheses were formulated, which are H1: Educational qualification will significantly influence turnover intentions among employees of the police academy; H2: Age will significantly influence turnover intentions among police academy employees; and H3: There will be a significant interaction effect of educational qualification and age on turnover intention among police academy employees. This study provides insights that could inform retention strategies and enhance

organizational stability in a specialized public higher institution.

Methods

Participants

Employees totalling seventy-five (75), comprising 70 (93.3%) males and only 5 (6.7%) females, whose ages range from 25 to 57, with a mean age of 42.8 years, were drawn using a purposive sampling method participated in the study. They were also assessed demographically on rank, qualification religious affiliation. Summary of these demographics indicates the rank of Lecturer I with the highest frequency of respondents, 37(49.3%), followed by Senior Lecturer, 23(30.7%), while the ranks of administrative officer, Assistant Registrar, and Clerical officer were nine (12%), four (5.3%) and two (2.7%) respectively.

On the factor of qualification, those with Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) degree had the highest frequency of 35(46.7%), closely followed by Master's degree 28(37.3), while First degree/Higher National Diploma (HND) and National Certificate in Education (NCE)/National Diploma (ND) were Eight (10.7%), and Four (5.3%) respectively. This response characteristic provides evidence that people with higher qualifications and academics, in particular, are more responsive to requests for participation in research activities. Again, among these participants, 53(70.3%) were Christians, while 22(29.7%) were Moslems.

Research Design

A cross-sectional survey research design was used for this study because self-reports are more appropriate for constructs that reflect subjective judgements about human experiences and behaviour. Once more, it was more economical financially and time-saving in the absence of research funding.

Instrument

Turnover intention is a three-item measure extracted from the Michigan Organisational Assessment Scale (Seashore et al., 1982). It is a five-point Likert scale. The three items are: 1) You frequently think about leaving your current organization; 2) It is likely that you will actively look for a job in the next year; and 3) You will probably look for a job in the next year. The Cronbach's alpha reliability ratio for turnover intention in this study was ($\alpha = .891$). All of the scale's items reflected high and acceptable response ratios among participants to warrant statistical analysis.

Procedure

After permission was granted by the ethics committee to conduct the study, participants were approached by the researcher at the Senate building, which houses offices for both faculty and support employees. The researcher explained the nature of the study and assured them that their personal information would be anonymous and responses would be confidentially treated for research purposes alone. Participants' consent was solicited, and those who agreed to participate were given the questionnaire to fill out and informed of their freedom to withdraw at any stage of the study. However, if they choose to go on, they should give honest responses to all the questions, as there are no right or wrong answers. The distribution and collection of the questionnaire was instantaneous as there were few items to complete. It took just a week to collect the entire data, but only fully completed questionnaires were considered and used in the analysis.

Data Analysis

Univariate analysis, specifically the two-way analysis of variance, which allows testing the impact of two independent variables (educational level, & age) on one dependent variable (turnover intention), was used. This

is because it has the capacity to analyse categorical variables.

Results

The following section presents all the results generated from data, beginning with descriptive to inferential analyses.

Table 1. Group summary means, standard deviations and number (N) of participants
Descriptive Statistics

Dependent Variable: Total Turnover Intention

What is your highest qualification?	What is your age? (Binned)	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
NCE/ND	Young	6.0000	2.00000	4
	Total	6.0000	2.00000	4
HND/First degree	Young	6.5000	3.54562	8
	Total	6.5000	3.54562	8
Masters	Young	12.6667	2.30940	12
	Middle	13.1111	2.36878	9
	Older	6.8571	.89974	7
	Total	11.3571	3.32459	28
PhD	Young	13.2222	2.72845	9
	Middle	11.3333	2.05971	12
	Older	9.2857	4.82667	14
	Total	11.0000	3.81945	35
Total	Young	10.5152	4.14669	33
	Middle	12.0952	2.32174	21
	Older	8.4762	4.09413	21
	Total	10.3867	3.91081	75

Table 1 above presents the means, standard deviations, and number of participants in each group of academic qualification (NCE/ND, HND/first Degree, Master's, and PhD) based on the age (Young, Middle, and Older). Both NCE/ND and 1st Degree qualifications had only the young age group means and standard deviations of 6.00, SD = 2.00; and 6.50, SD = 3.55; N = 4 each, respectively. Master's degree qualification has a young age group mean of 12.67, SD = 2.31, and N = 12. Again, Master's degree qualification has a middle age mean of 13.11, SD = 2.37, and N = 9. Finally,

the Master's degree versus the older age group has a mean of 6.86, SD = 0.90, N = 7 participants. At the PhD level of educational qualification, the young age group N = 9 had a mean of 13.22, and SD of 2.73, while the middle age group mean was 11.33, SD = 2.10, N = 12 participants. Finally, the older age group with a PhD had a mean of 9.29, SD = 4.83, and 14 participants. Table 2 below provides the results of the between-subjects effects of educational qualifications and age on turnover intention among police academy employees.

**Table 2. Summary of two-way ANOVA for the test of hypotheses
Test of between-subjects effects**

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	423.775 ^a	5	84.755	8.260	.000	.374
Intercept	3216.222	1	3216.222	313.440	.000	.820
Quali	352.412	3	117.471	11.448	.000	.332
Age2	180.633	1	180.633	17.604	.000	.203
Quali * Age2	21.411	1	21.411	2.087	.153	.029
Error	708.012	69	10.261			
Total	9223.000	75				
Corrected Total	1131.787	74				

A two-way between-groups analysis of variance was used to explore the effect of educational qualifications and age on levels of turnover intention among Police academy employees, as measured by the Turnover Intention Scale (Seashore et al., 1982). Participants' academic qualifications were classified according to four levels of education (NCE/ND, 1st Degree/HND, Master's degree, and PhD), while age was binned at three categories (≤ 40 years = Young, 41 – 44 years = Midage and 45+ = Older). As shown in above table 2, the interaction effect between qualification and age on turnover intention was not statistically significant, $F(2, 67) = 2.37, p = .10$. There was a statistically significant main effect for educational qualification, $F(3, 67) = 12.02, p = .005$; with a large effect size (partial eta squared = .35). Post-hoc comparisons using the Tukey HSD test indicated that the mean scores for those with NCE/ND and first degree/HND ($M = 6.00, SD = 2.00, & M = 6.50, SD = 3.55$) significantly differed from both the Master's degree and PhDs ($M = 11.36, SD = 3.33, & M = 11.00, SD = 3.82$). Similarly, the main effect of age, $F(2, 67) = 14.47, p = .005$, was also statistically significant with a large effect size (partial eta squared=.30 approximately). The post-hoc

comparisons indicated that the older age group mean was significantly different from both the young and middle age groups.

Figure 1 below shows that turnover intention was highest for both young and middle age groups with Master's and PhD degrees as academic qualifications. For the young age group, turnover intention progressively increased slowly from NCE/ND to first degree/HND, and spiked higher above the grand mean line at Master's level and peaked at PhD. This result shows that the young age group featured in each educational category reflected positive incremental turnover intentions at each higher level of educational attainment. While the middle and older age groups were found only at the Master's and PhD educational categories, the middle age group's turnover intention reaches its highest at the Master's level above the young age group, but diminishes at the PhD level. This may indicate loss of aspiration or perception of alternative employment opportunities at middle age, going to older or because of organisational commitment. Finally, the older age group's turnover intention increased from Master's to PhD, but was well below the grand mean. In summary, the ANOVA result suggests that there exist changes in turnover

intentions scores across the employees' different levels of qualification and ages.

Figure 1. Differences in levels of academic qualification and age, and their effect on employee turnover intentions

Discussion and Conclusion

The findings of this research highlight the complex interplay between educational qualification and age in determining turnover intention among police academy employees. Educational qualifications and age appear interrelated and independently influence turnover intentions. For example, both young and middle-aged employees with Master's degree qualifications are more likely to consider leaving the academy. Interestingly, while the young age group's intentions to leave increased proportionately with the attainment of a PhD, the turnover intention topped out at the Master's degree for the middle age group and began to decline thereafter. This is possible due to a vibrant health to aid career mobility, perceived available career opportunities and higher career aspirations (Ng & Feldman, 2010; Ukeh & Nyam, 2023). On the other hand, older employees with master's degree qualifications tend to show lower turnover intention than those with PhDs, possibly due to fewer alternative opportunities and greater institutional commitment or sheer stability.

The implications of these results for the first and second hypotheses are that turnover intentions of academy employees are highest

only for the young and middle age groups with Master's and PhD degrees. These findings are in tandem with the human capital theory (Becker, 1975), which suggests that employees with higher educational qualifications may have greater opportunities and options in the job market, potentially increasing their turnover intentions. Similarly, age can influence turnover intentions, with younger employees possibly seeking career advancement and older employees considering retirement or career changes.

Specifically, the first hypothesis, which states that educational qualifications will significantly influence turnover intentions among police academy employees, is ably supported by the present result and is therefore accepted. Turnover intention was lowest for the NCE/ND and 1st degree levels of educational qualification than master's and PhD, as indicated by the slope. This result shows that employees' intention to quit the academy is a function of the type of qualification they hold.

The finding of this study is consistent with Lin et al. (2023), who found that turnover intention was significantly influenced by marriage, education, age and other factors. According to Lin and colleagues, their study among medical staff in rural medical institutions of China reveals that staff who had a bachelor's degree or above and were intermediate professionals are more likely to leave than those with higher qualifications. This study result is in harmony with Akpa and Asikhia (2016), who found that educational attainment has a significant influence on the intention of employees to leave their universities. Nevertheless, some research evidence did not agree with the findings of this study. For example, Abukari and Alhassan's findings among teachers in the Ghana Education Service did not find that educational qualification influenced their

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intention to quit (Abukari & Alhassan, 2021). Their findings may also be reasonable as there could be other factors (age, job satisfaction, leadership styles, etc.), which can mediate or moderate the relationship between educational qualifications and intention to leave.

Again, Ajayi and Olatunji (2017), while exploring differences in intention to leave among Nigerian high school teachers across various demographic variables, did not find significant differences in turnover intention based on academic qualifications. The authors conclude that teachers are likely to consider turnover due to various factors, including their age and tenure, and this consideration is likely to occur regardless of their qualifications. The migration of most young medical doctors and academics with higher degrees from Nigeria in particular and Africa in general to other parts of the world may be accounted for by perceived available job opportunities and better conditions of service for those with such qualifications.

Once more, the second hypothesis, which states that age will significantly affect turnover intentions among police academy employees, significant differences were found among the groups and is accepted. This finding implies that the younger employees experienced higher turnover intention than the middle and older ones (Akpa & Asikhia, 2016). While the effect relationship between age and turnover intention for the young age group was positively related, that of the middle age group was negatively related. The implication of this result for the middle age is that the younger the age, the higher the intention to leave, while the older, the lower the intention to leave the academy (Akpa & Asikhia, 2016; Gessesse & Premanandam, 2024; Mulie & Sime, 2018). The older age group's relationship, on the other hand, was positively related to turnover intention but fell below the observed grand mean.

This finding is consistent with earlier studies (Gessesse & Premanandam, 2024; Lin et al., 2023; Mulie & Sime, 2018). For example, Mulie & Sime in their research among academic staff among selected Ethiopian universities factually provided a reason for variation in turnover intention because of age. They emphasise that when an employee's age increases, their affective and continuance commitment also increase, and consequently their turnover intention decreases (Mulie & Sime, 2018). Similarly, Gessesse & Premanadam's study of gender, age, and turnover intention among academic employees in higher education institutions in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia showed that middle age group of academic employees has significantly higher intention to leave than the younger and relatively older age groups (Gessesse & Premanadam, 2024). Lin and colleagues' findings also collaborate highly with those of this study and related literature. They opine that at age 41-50 years old and above, which is indicative of the older age group depicted in this study, coupled with high human resources management practices and high job satisfaction, effectively reduces the odds against employees' intention to leave the current organisation (Lin et al., 2023). Furthermore, another research that supports the findings of this study is Ajayi and Olatunji's (2017). The study found that the age group 36-45 years was the least willing to quit. While teachers aged 55 years and above, and those aged below 35 years, were most willing to quit their jobs.

However, the third and final hypothesis, which posits that both academic qualification and age will significantly affect turnover intention among police academy employees, was rejected. Otherwise stated, there was no interaction effect of academic qualification and age on turnover intention. That is, the different categories of academic qualifications did not depend on age to exert their influence

on the turnover intention of police academy employees. The fact that the interaction effect in this study was not statistically significant does not preclude the possibility of reciprocal action between educational level and age in relation to turnover intention. The small sample size used in this study and the response pattern of participants may also account for the results.

Considering the findings of this study, it is concluded that though complex factors influence employees' intention to leave an organisation, educational qualification and age play significant roles in shaping their decisions to stay or leave. Higher education institutions must adopt tailored strategies to address these demographic factors to ensure a supportive and fulfilling work environment for the well-being of employees.

Implications

These results suggest that retention strategies should be tailored to different segments of employees. For younger, highly qualified academics, institutions might focus on providing career development opportunities and pathways for advancement within the academy. For older staff with lower qualifications, strategies might emphasize job security and recognition of their contributions.

Limitations and Future Research

The study's cross-sectional design limits the ability to draw causal inferences. Longitudinal or qualitative in-depth studies could provide more robust insights into the dynamics of turnover intention. Additionally, future research could explore other potential moderators, such as job satisfaction and organizational commitment, to develop a more comprehensive understanding of turnover intention in higher institutions.

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